

Analyzing and evaluating critical cyber security challenges faced by vendor organizations in software development: SLR based approach

¹Kawthar Muhammad, ²Dr A. Senthil kumar

¹ Level 800, Department of Software Engineering, School of Postgraduate Studies,

² Dean, School of Science and Information Technology, Skyline University Nigeria.

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Abstract

Security is the defense against many threats, and most businesses struggle with security, particularly with cyber-attacks. Because of the quick rise in threats, supervised and pattern-based detection algorithms used in cyber security are still the same and provide ongoing security. Noticing. Vendor firms face a variety of issues, including cyber theft, the most frequent form of cyber-attack. In order to help vendor firms, identify cyber security challenges during software development, this research study is establishing the Cyber Security Challenges Model (CSCM). By creating a search string based on research questions, a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) is carried out on 44 pertinent research publications to identify cyber security issues/challenges. As the last

Keyword---Cyber security, Challenges, SLR, vendor, Software Development, SPSS

Introduction

The most crucial problem in the digital age is identifying security threats, which calls for in-depth knowledge of security-based technology [1]. For businesses and Security in businesses can be discussed in a number of ways, including cyber, information, and computer security. [2]. "The preservation of particulars/information and its analytical components, comprising of the systems and hardware that use, reserve, and impart that particulars/information" is the definition of information security. [3]. Details Information security is not a universally accepted concept, either [5]. There doesn't seem to be any documentation that distinguishes between information security and cyber security theory or the relationship between the two. The topic of "information security" can be crucial for Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs)) "information security" can turn out to be an important matter and many times used as cyber security [6].

Nowadays organizations encounter difficulty to protect themselves from potential cyber-attacks [7]. The International Telecommunications Union (ITU) defines cyber security as: Cyber Security is the collection of instruments, strategies, security concepts, suggestions, measures, instructions, and technologies that could be useful while safeguarding the cyber environment, firm, and user resources. Cyber Security [8] is turning out to be important stuff of worldwide attentiveness and significance. The cyber violations that took place at Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are nearly 72%. This is why at some layers SMEs require security services [9]. With obvious and shared characteristics, IT security commonly concentrated on guarding networked computer resources/assets [10]. To oppose the threats of cyber-attacks Cyber security advocates, try to encourage security top applications and the acquisition

of security technology [11].

Cyber security is a computing-based discipline that in the presence of challenges and threat line up resources of the network and human and processes to corroborate “Assured Operation”. Nowadays, cyber security has turned out to be one of the most severe financial and nationwide security issues [12]. Due to the fact, that the internet provides the phantasm – and, every so often, the fact – of anonymity, those wishing to pursue criminal hobbies discover the net as a secure and resourceful ground for their efforts. One of these activities enabled through the Internet and the modern-day World Wide Web (from time to time cited as “internet 2.0”), is cyber stalking [13].

DoS transmissions also can be applied to execute far-flung records spoofing from random factors. An attacker should assemble malicious streams of message records to shape all subscriber pastimes that could be dispatched to the DCS service event for advertising. Subsequent subscribers might then unknowingly take delivery of the malicious packets through relied-on DCS event services. The 2007 cyber assaults on Estonia consisted of DDoS assaults that crippled the country’s banks and parliament capabilities. The assaults concerned ping floods and the “botnet” era such that the DDoS assault technique changed into a complexity now no longer visible before. Researchers and navy planners concur that the coaching at the back of the DDoS assaults has been the second-biggest example of state-backed cyber warfare [14].

In a hit attack, the loss to the victim (the metropolis and its citizens) and the advantage to the hacker may be notably asymmetric, with the loss in large part exceeding the advantage [15]. According to records from the Russian facts protection certification system, approximately one 1/3 of the portions of the software program examined exhibited vulnerabilities at some stage in a two-12 months study [16]. The vulnerability might be a code flaw this is intentional or unintended and won’t appear to be malicious code

Instead of attempting to create entire, fully tested PC systems, most developers simply focus on verifying smaller, more vulnerable, or significant portions of a system. As long as those individuals remain negligent and ignorant about their role in improving cyber security, the nation's cyber security will remain weak [18]. According to a Symantec survey conducted among 20,000 people across 24 countries, 69% of respondents stated that they had experienced a cyber-attack at some point in their lives. Symantec estimated that those 14 adults experience a cyber-attack every second or more than a million assaults every day, without regard to distance or geography [19]

Related Work

Information security and cyber security differ in terms of threats, weaknesses, and resources. There are several resource concerns that are involved with security [8]. In addition to technical expertise and abilities, an effective cyber security advocate also has to understand the larger picture [11]. In order to address every vulnerability that is mentioned, the authors [7] propose a model with unique cyber security information. Information and resources, as well as the person or people using them in the cyber environment, are all relevant to cyber security [8]. Ease of access, the ability to store data in a relatively little amount of space, the loss of proof, etc. are common causes of cyber-attacks.

Since the current models rely on signatures, an attacker might easily initiate an attack by making small adjustments to the syntactical depiction of the signature [21]. At least 255,100 phishing assaults have place globally in 2016 [22]. The distribution of costs and advantages may occur if each business maintains its security to optimize the benefits of the internet [23]. Companies establish safe systems that support professional workers' and employees' behavior preservation and improvement. Employees who don't have an organizational system often perform poorly on a daily basis [24]. Numerous occurrences have included the unencrypted USB tool and malware rights being removed, as well as protocols involving external email being violated.

Cybercriminals have frequently breached secure, well-designed user structures by taking advantage of people's negligence or by purposefully tricking them, like by posing as the device administrator and requesting passwords [25]. Cyber security risks on the internet encompass a wide range of potentially illegal activity. The term "cybercrimes" is primarily divided into three categories: cybercrimes against individuals, (ii) against all forms of property, and (iii) against the government. [8]–[21] covers a wide variety of legal acts, including cyber theft, software piracy, cyber terrorism, spam, credit card information theft, denial of service, cyber bullying, and digital media.

Computer as the Target: property theft, theft of advertising facts (buyer list, price information, or advertising strategy), and blackmail based mostly on information gleaned from automated files (clinical facts, private history, or sexual inclination) [26]. A challenge in safety management is providing an accurate evaluation of different safety plans and estimating the costs and benefits of technology in the absence of actual data [27]. Cybercrimes are categorized into three main categories: sending offensive emails to others, illegally accessing other people's computers through the use of various spyware programs, and stealing personal information from websites that violate government regulations. Organizations suffer financial losses of millions of dollars as a result.

Upon examining the relevant literature, it's possible that neither the attack categories nor the underlying methods exist [28]. The attacker needs a basic understanding of professional conduct and the message transfer protocols in order to launch an attack [29]. When customers are unable to discriminate between a secure product and one that is well-built, the enterprise product has an advantage and enters the market first [30]. If the reaction is unaware of the attack's nature, it is impossible to respond in a timely manner [31]. The whole society, companies, and research community will be affected by the aberrant impacts of cybercrimes if this issue is not resolved in a timely manner [32]–[34].

Methodology

Finding pertinent papers using a procedure called Systematic Literature Review (SLR) is dependent on the research topics. The three stages of it are conducting, reporting, and planning. SLR is more reliable than standard literature reviews since it mimics a methodical approach to assessment. A methodical approach is used to find cyber security problems, with papers being chosen according to how well they relate to the topic or search term. A criterion for inclusion and exclusion is utilized to exclude irrelevant articles from a subset of research papers. Selected articles are searched for pertinent information, and the publication process's caliber is examined. The purpose of this essay is to draw attention to the cyber security issues that vendor companies encounter while developing software.

Identifying synonyms, validating and confirming terms in pertinent literature, utilizing Boolean operators for accurate results, and identifying outcomes, population, and intervention are all included in the SLR search string. Five databases were used for a trial search, but the outcomes weren't as good. Although the final Science Direct search phrase was not very long, it produced results from relevant paper investigation. A final selection of research papers was made using an insertion/removal criterion.

Period wise list of challenges.

Name of Database	Search Result	Primary Selection	Final Selection
Google Scholar	13900	81	37
IEEE	55	02	00
SpringerLink	2074	33	03
ACM	398	22	00
ScienceDirect	4795	31	04
Total	21222	169	44
After selecting 23 papers in Snow Bowling Technique (Total)			67

Table 1 displays the results of the examination of relevant publications that were generated using the final search string.

Table 1 illustrates how the inclusion/exclusion criterion was applied in the final selection of research publications, together with an insertion/removal criterion. Through reading, we have chosen the pertinent materials on paper quality and verification for this procedure.

III. RESULTS

CHALLENGES/BARRIERS/ISSUES FIND THROUGH SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

The study identifies critical cyber security challenges for vendors companies by analyzing research articles reviewed via SLR. Key challenges include increasing cyber-attacks and cyber-crimes, lack of right knowledge (48%), framework (48%), technical support (43%), disaster issues (40%), cost security (39%), confidentiality and trust (37%), management (33%), unauthorized access (31%), and lack of resources (28%). Security issues/access of cyber-attacks refer to the increasing number of cyber-attacks and cyber-crimes, which can be harmful, diverse, and troublesome. Lack of knowledge about intellectual property rights, products, and policies of software is another critical challenge. Frameworks must focus on root causes and unite expertise from various disciplines to address technological and social aspects of cyber security.

Disaster issues (40%), cost security (39%), confidentiality and trust (37%), management (33%), and unauthorized access (31%) are also identified as critical challenges. Cost security issues involve serious economic, investment, and financial issues faced by vendor organizations, with nearly 431 million users victimized and their financial losses increasing to 388 billion dollars. Lack of management (33%), unauthorized access (31%), and lack of resources (28%) are also critical challenges. Misallocation of resources due to economically stable decision-making in security can lead to misallocation of resources. Lastly, lack of metrics (28%) is another critical challenge, involving meaningful metrics, proactive cyber security measures, and lack of impact or bad impact issues on software or software development. These challenges highlight the need for vendors to prioritize cyber security measures and develop robust frameworks to protect against cyber threats.

Analysis of the Cyber Security Challenges Identified Through SLR for Vendor Organizations

The SLR analysis reveals the challenges identified through a statistical analysis of continents, period, and organization size, indicating the effectiveness of the thirteen identified challenges.

This study focuses on analyzing cyber security challenges across six continents: Europe, North America, Asia, Africa, Australia, and Mixed. The goal is to determine if these challenges are different or remain the same or constant. The data set was created using SPSS and Chi-square Test (linear by linear association) to find significant differences between the identified challenges. The results show more similarities than differences among the challenges over various continents. The total number of challenges cited in various continents is 13 in Europe, North America, and Mixed, while the other challenges have no occurrences in one continent. The challenge of lack of quality, liability, and reliability has zero occurrences in three continents, while other challenges have no occurrences in one continent.

The study also analyzes cyber security challenges period-wise, considering two periods from 2001-2010 and 2011-2020. A linear-by-linear association chi-square test is used to understand the significant difference between the two periods. A total of 13 challenges have been identified for both periods, with no changes occurring in all the challenges over two periods. However, the identified challenges lack metrics in Australia. The most critical challenge in both periods is security issues/access of cyber-attacks (43%-62%). A sudden increase in the second period indicates that software

vendor organizations have not taken this issue seriously. This non-serious behavior of software vendor organizations needs to be considered a serious issue to overcome its rapid increase.

Some of the critical challenges faced by vendors organizations during software development include disaster issues (71%-32%), cost security issues (57%-34%), unauthorized access issues (43%-28%), lack of metrics (29%-28%), and managerial blunders (29%-26%). The decrease in challenges in the second period shows the seriousness and priority of software vendor organizations towards the second period. However, the main drawback of smart technologies is that they can make cities possible victims of cyber-attacks. In 2011, approximately US\$114 billion of cybercrime was performed in 24 different countries. To prevent and detect attacks, organizations should take strict actions to prevent and detect cyber-attacks. Other challenges include framework (43%-49%), lack of technical support (21%-49%), lack of confidentiality and trust (29%-40%), lack of management (21%-36%), and lack of resources (14%-32%).

The study reveals that two cyber security challenges, disaster issues and lack of quality, liability, and reliability, were significantly different between two periods. These challenges were high in the first period and low in the second period, possibly due to software vendor organizations taking these challenges seriously. The correlation coefficient between the first and second periods is 0.157, indicating a strong relationship. The study uses a sample size of 67 papers, with 66 organizations classified as small, medium, or large. The Australian Bureau of Statistics categorizes organizations based on their size, with medium-sized organizations having four barriers cited in over 46% of papers with 13 cyber security issues. These challenges include lack of right knowledge, disaster issues, cost security issues, and security issues/access of cyber-attacks. Small-sized organizations have nine challenges cited in over 40% of papers with 13 cyber security challenges. These challenges include lack of right knowledge, security issues/access of cyber-attacks, administrative mistakes during development, framework, technical support, disaster issues, cost security issues, lack of management, and lack of quality, liability, and reliability. The study concludes that security issues/access of cyber-attacks, lack of right knowledge, and disaster issues are critical challenges for all large, medium, and small-sized organizations. The linear-by-linear Chi-square test was used to identify statistically notable variations among the 13 identified cyber security challenges based on various organization sizes. The Anova One Way Factor was used for statistical comparison.

Limitation

Many studies on cyber security challenges have not reported the genuine reasons behind their impact on vendor organizations and software development. This may be due to publication bias in literature assessment, surveys, and case research. Due to a small ratio of work in the field, the study found only 44 papers for data extraction, which was insufficient for the required results. To address this, a snow bowling technique was used, resulting in 67 papers for data extraction.

Conclusion

The vendor organizations need to give proper attention to these critical challenges to avoid any risk of failure by addressing these challenges. Furthermore, it also intended to find the practices for these critical cyber security challenges and will try to help the vendor organizations through these identified practices.

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